

Opinions and Perspective**Effectiveness of including “Alternative Systems of Medicine” in foundation course of First MBBS Students according to CBME (new curriculum) for 2019 Batch****Dr. Shabana Sultana¹, Dr. Pulluri Sadanandam *², Dr. Ramagalla Amrutha Roopa³, Dr. Aparna Vedapriya. K⁴**

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Abstract

Introduction: Definition of traditional medicine according to WHO - traditional medicine includes diverse health practices, approaches, knowledge and beliefs incorporating plant, animal, mineral based medicines, spiritual therapies, manual techniques and exercises which can be used to maintain well-being, as well as to treat, diagnose or prevent illness. Hence the knowledge gained so will definitely help the Medical students who are future practitioners to maintain self complete health and also effectively take care of patients' complete health.

Aim: The aim of the study was to know how far this topic has benefitted the first MBBS students to effectively apply the alternative system of medicine along with modern medicine during their clinical practice

Methods: This was a questionnaire based study where 100 first professional MBBS students of Apollo Medical College, Hyderabad, were asked to fill anonymously a questionnaire about their perceptions of this topic. The results were analyzed to see if there was any use of learning about alternative system of medicine.

Results: The majority of the medical students (99.7%) opined that alternative system of medicine topic is very useful, while only 0.3% of students were indifferent about it.

Conclusion: Most of the students clearly preferred and accepted the use of alternative system of medicine for the benefit of personal health and patient care in future. To apply the knowledge of various medical subjects learnt during MBBS curriculum, with the interrelationships between Alternative systems of medicine using as interprofessional collaboration for the betterment of self and society's health as a whole.

Keywords: Alternative system of medicine, medical students, MBBS foundation course, curriculum, interprofessional collaboration, complete health.

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Introduction

In the year 1970s interest in the use of practitioners of traditional medicine in primary health care was growing. Since 1974, traditional medicine has been incorporated in relevant WHO programs and in October 1976 representatives of WHO's regional offices met in New Delhi and proposed certain program objectives.[1] The 1978 Declaration of Alma-Ata referred to the need for a variety of health workers, including traditional practitioners.[2] In 1983 WHO published a collection of 29 essays as a reader in order to provide guidance for health administrators and practitioners.[3] Traditional alternative medicine may include (AYUSH - Ayurveda, Yoga & Naturopathy, Unani, Siddha and Homeopathy systems of medicine). This field includes the more mainstream and accepted forms of therapy, such as Ayurveda , Yoga , Unani, Siddha, Homeopathy, , Naturopathy (part of Naturopathy - Pranayama, Meditation, Nutrition/diet, Massage, Chinese Chiropractic and osteopathic medicine, Electromagnetic therapy etc). These therapies have been practiced for centuries worldwide with successful results. (Johns Hopkins Medicine). Traditional alternative medicine is definitely on a rise. This has been used now for centuries. Natural remedies also help with healing and treat a person disease. Alternative medicine unlike any other medicine has no side effects. These remedies are design to be giving in small dose to treat a symptom. According to

Niggemann & Gubber A herb containing a wide variety of (mostly unknown) substances may well include some with unwanted effects; a treatment method using a mechanical procedure may lead to injuries; and a healer without adequate education may be a cause of increased diagnostic and treatment faults (Niggemann & Grubber 2018, Bartleyby Research).

Materials and Methods:

100 Students of first year MBBS Apollo Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Hyderabad, Telangana State in India, were selected for study. They were given feedback form immediately after the general lecture of "Alternative Systems of Medicine" in foundation course according to CBME (new curriculum) for 2019 Batch so as to know the overall effectiveness of this topic Short briefing was done regarding the study after which verbal consent was taken to confirm their participation. After the lecture, questionnaire was circulated to all the students and feedback was taken. Alternative Systems of Medicine" during foundation course. Overall satisfaction of the students with this method of lecture delivery was assessed. Students were asked to answer the following questionnaire, to know their preference for this type of teaching methodology. The student were given following questionnaire to rank the following with Likert scale where the scale could be augmented by written comments given below.

MBBS- 1ST Year – 2019 Batch ; Foundation course
Students feedback - *Alternative Systems of Medicine* –Dr. Shabana Sulthana

1	What is the impact of lecture	1. 2. 3.
2	So what are the points to be added or deleted	1. 2. 3.
3	Points that further need clarification	
4	Facilitating factors 'AHA' moment of the session	
5	Hindering factors 'OHO' moment of the session	
6	The session was well organized	
7	The session gave orientation of the topic	
8	Quality of the syllabus and teaching material	
9	What next ? How will you use this knowledge	
10	Any other comments	

A total of 100 medical students participated voluntarily in the study and completed the

questionnaire. The result was tabulated. The above answers to the questions were analyzed,

the predilections of the students were assessed after compilation of these questionnaire by summing up the feedback for each method. Also it was analyzed whether there is a preference of any particular aspect of Alternative Systems of Medicine.

Results:

The majority of the medical students (98.7%) preferred Alternative Systems of Medicine

topic in foundation course very useful, while only 1.3% of students were indifferent. The students' overall preferences are given as follows in students' own words choosing all different types of opinions and pasting the ones which summarizes all students' opinions at the best.

Few photos of students' feedback

Apollo Institute of Medical Sciences and Research
MBBS- 1st Year - 2019 Batch, Foundation course
Students feedback - Alternative systems of medicine - Dr. Shabana

1	What happened	1. I got to know about diff alternative systems of medicine. 2. Different kinds of diseases can be cured differently. 3.
2	So what	1. It can be used during my career. 2. I can share this knowledge. 3. It is really important.
3	Points that further need clarification	Is Yoga & music therapy really helpful.
4	Facilitating factors 'AHA' moment of the session	Diff. kinds of therapy to treat.
5	Hindering factors 'OHO' moment of the session	Not my 'OHO' moment for me.
6	The session was well organized	Yes
7	The session gave orientation of the topic	Yes
8	Quality of the syllabus and teaching material	Nice
9	What next? How will you use this knowledge	I will suggest my patients if needed.
10	Any other comments	

Apollo Institute of Medical Sciences and Research
MBBS- 1st Year - 2019 Batch, Foundation course
Students feedback - Alternative systems of medicine - Dr. Shabana

1	What happened	1. We were taught about AYUSH courses. 2. Got to know about other alternative courses. 3.
2	So what	1. we got an idea about the alternative med. system of medicine. 2. 3.
3	Points that further need clarification	-
4	Facilitating factors 'AHA' moment of the session	There are many alternate methods coming up other than allopathy, which improves human welfare.
5	Hindering factors 'OHO' moment of the session	-
6	The session was well organized	Yes
7	The session gave orientation of the topic	Alternative systems of medicine.
8	Quality of the syllabus and teaching material	
9	What next? How will you use this knowledge	
10	Any other comments	

Apollo Institute of Medical Sciences and Research
MBBS- 1st Year - 2019 Batch, Foundation course
Students feedback - Alternative systems of medicine - Dr. Shabana

1	What happened	1. she taught us about AYUSH 2. elaborated on holistic medicine. 3. Health using conventional methods.
2	So what	1. I was enlightened 2. I was inspired. 3. I am more open to different practices now.
3	Points that further need clarification	-
4	Facilitating factors 'AHA' moment of the session	-
5	Hindering factors 'OHO' moment of the session	-
6	The session was well organized	Yes
7	The session gave orientation of the topic	Yes
8	Quality of the syllabus and teaching material	Good
9	What next? How will you use this knowledge	I will use it to become better.
10	Any other comments	No.

Apollo Institute of Medical Sciences and Research
MBBS- 1st Year - 2019 Batch, Foundation course
Students feedback - Alternative systems of medicine - Dr. Shabana

1	What happened	1. It highlighted about different alternative systems. 2. Explained about diseases that can be cured by it. 3. Helped to understand importance of AYUSH.
2	So what	1. Helped to understand importance of AYUSH. 2. 3.
3	Points that further need clarification	None.
4	Facilitating factors 'AHA' moment of the session	
5	Hindering factors 'OHO' moment of the session	None
6	The session was well organized	Yes.
7	The session gave orientation of the topic	alternative systems of medicine
8	Quality of the syllabus and teaching material	Good.
9	What next? How will you use this knowledge	To respect AYUSH practitioners as well.
10	Any other comments	

Apollo Institute of Medical Sciences and Research
MBBS- 1st Year - 2019 Batch ; Foundation course
Students feedback - Alternative systems of medicine - Dr. Shabana

1	What happened	1. Ppt Presentation 2. AYUSH medicinal practices 3. Homeopathy.
2	So what	1. Even alternative medicine has 2. Some form of logic or proof of concept that needs to be researched and better understood
3	Points that further need clarification	
4	Facilitating factors 'AHA' moment of the session	Even AYUSH has some cases in which the therapy actually works even if actual scientific cause is not known.
5	Hindering factors 'OHO' moment of the session	
6	The session was well organized	Yes.
7	The session gave orientation of the topic	Yes.
8	Quality of the syllabus and teaching material	Decent
9	What next ? How will you use this knowledge	To be not completely dismissal of practices other than allopathy.
10	Any other comments	No.

Apollo Institute of Medical Sciences and Research
MBBS- 1st Year - 2019 Batch ; Foundation course
Students feedback - Alternative systems of medicine - Dr. Shabana

1	What happened	1. Alternative medical services were introduced 2. Their effectiveness, accessibility & affordability were discussed. 3. The pros & cons of such systems were addressed
2	So what	1. Such systems are present as they are the conventional & cater to the immediate needs of the patient. 3.
3	Points that further need clarification	-
4	Facilitating factors 'AHA' moment of the session	The benefits of such systems
5	Hindering factors 'OHO' moment of the session	Time constraints
6	The session was well organized	Yes
7	The session gave orientation of the topic	Yes.
8	Quality of the syllabus and teaching material	Good.
9	What next ? How will you use this knowledge	To provide better care.
10	Any other comments	

Discussion:

The term AYUSH stands for Ayurveda, Yoga & Naturopathy, Unani, Siddha and Homeopathy systems of medicine. This system of medicine is more preventive than curative. It teaches the daily healthy lifestyle aspects to maintain oneself healthy[4]. Sedantary lifestyle like addiction to phone, among people is leading to non communicable diseases like under nutrition and over nutrition (obesity), Hypertension, Diabetes mellitus, common mental disorders related to stress and anxiety. Prevalence of non communicable and mental illness in India is increasing day by day[5]. Unhealthy dietary practices of eating junk food has become too common among people because of easy availability of such foods and due to lack of awareness of importance of food as medicine. AYUSH system of medicine clearly explains the importance of natural healthy diet, fasting, *asthanga yoga*, *pranayama*, meditation, manipulative therapeutics and various forms of therapies in the prevention and treatment of many chronic

diseases which has been proved by evidence based medicine. Alternative Systems of Medicine application helps in prevention of such diseases and restoration of health. The National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) came into play in 2005 but implemented at ground level in 2006 and introduced the scheme of “Mainstreaming of AYUSH and revitalization of local health traditions” to strengthen public health services. This scheme is currently in operation in its second phase, since 1st April 2012, with the 12th 5-year plan[6]. After the implementation of this scheme AYUSH Dispensary is started in every PHC (Primary health centre), CHC (Community health centre) so as to be reachable to each and every person in rural India. Implementation of Alternative Systems of Medicine through AYUSH services has effectively cured many long term illnesses[7].

Advantages of this Method:

It treats the underlying cause hence heals the body. It improves of the quality of life through physical, mental and spiritual enlightenment.

Application of alternative medicine results in drastic improvement in the quality of life a person has. It helps in both prevention and treatment of disease[8]. Alternative medicine system is used to cure the diseases through wide spectrum of therapies, which are safer without side effects. It is more flexible[9]. Studies have shown the beneficial use of Alternative Medicine in cancer patients as an

active way to manage the physical, psychological, and spiritual consequences of cancer[10]. Specific integrative therapies can be recommended as evidence-based supportive care options during breast cancer treatment. Most integrative therapies require further investigation via well-designed controlled trials with meaningful outcomes[11]

Symptom	Complementary Medicine Technique
Pain	Acupuncture Chiropractic therapy Hypnosis Massage Reiki Shiatsu
Nausea/Vomiting	Acupuncture Aromatherapy Hypnosis Progressive muscle relaxation Shiatsu
Fatigue	Acupuncture Massage Meditation Reiki Tai chi Yoga
High blood pressure	Aromatherapy
Hot flashes	Acupuncture
Headache	Chiropractic therapy Shiatsu
Muscle tension	Aromatherapy Massage Shiatsu

Emotional symptoms

Symptom	Complementary Medicine Technique
Anxiety/Stress/Fear	Aromatherapy Guided imagery Hypnosis Journaling Massage Meditation Progressive muscle relaxation Prayer Support groups Tai chi Yoga
Depression	Aromatherapy Guided imagery Journaling Progressive muscle relaxation

Disadvantages of this Method:

There is Minimal scientific research with limited evidence. It takes longer term for treatment though the procedures can be quick and easy[12]. This system is not useful in emergency cases. The disadvantages of these therapies include the lack of standardization of either the practice or the dispensing of the therapies and techniques[13]. All herbs have not been studied regarding their security and efficiency. There may be problems concerning their purity and their use in conventional treatments[14].

Conclusion:

As Alternative Systems of Medicine is very useful as supportive medicine therefore the knowledge gained by students can be well self practiced to maintain good health and at the same time it can be implemented during practice for the betterment of patients' health. The clear understanding of AYUSH (Ayurveda, Yoga & Naturopathy, Unani, Siddha and Homeopathy systems of medicine) and other complementary medicines will help in prevention and treatment of many chronic diseases like Obesity, Hypertension, Diabetes,

Osteoarthritis and COPD'S (chronic obstructive pulmonary disease) etc. As there is Lack of adequate or accepted research methodology for evaluating traditional medicine, there are many challenges to the safety and effective use of traditional medicine. The WHO Strategy will meet the gaps and challenges facilitating the contribution of Traditional Medicine to human health care in the 21st and coming centuries. It can be well concluded that Alternative Systems of Medicine is useful in prevention and treatment of disease. Therefore developed countries are looking to herbal medicines beyond their nutritional value. Finally "Let food be your medicine and let medicine be your food – Hippocrates" will make the students understand and implement this system.

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Authors Contribution :

Dr. Sadanandam has conceptualized and gathered the data concerning this work. Dr. Amrutha Roopa Ramagalla, Dr. K.Aparna Vedapriya has given the necessary inputs towards designing manuscript. All authors discussed the methodology and results together and contributed to the final manuscript.

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